

Goals, Work Programme and Status of the Advanced Core Physics Studies of Boron-Free LW-SMR Cores within the EU EASI-SMR Project

V. H. Sanchez-Espinoza^{1,*}, L. Mercatali¹, G. Prulhiere², R. Tuominen³, M. Tibergera⁴, E. Fridman⁵

¹Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany

²French Atomic Energy and Alternative Energy Commission (CEA) DES/IRESNE/DER/SPRC/LE2C Cadarache, Bldg. 230 F-13108 Saint-Paul-Lez-Durance, France

³VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd. P.O. Box 1000, FI-02044 VTT, Finland

⁴EDF R&D, EDF Lab Paris-Saclay, bd. Gaspard Monge 91120 Palaiseau, France

⁵Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf e.V, Bautzner Landstraße 400, 01328 Dresden, Germany

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the objectives, methodology, and current progress of the advanced core physics studies carried out within the EU-funded EASI-SMR project. The work focuses on boron-free light-water small modular reactor (LW-SMR) cores, aiming to improve the understanding of their neutronic behaviour, reactivity control mechanisms, and Multiphysics coupling effects. Two reference designs are investigated: the PRATIC core, an academic soluble-boron-free PWR benchmark developed by CEA, and the LDR lite, a public benchmark version of the LDR-50 district heating reactor originally developed at VTT and now commercialized by Steady Energy Oy. Both cores provide complementary frameworks for validating industrial analysis tools and exploring modelling challenges typical of compact boron-free reactors, such as strong leakage effects, heterogeneous absorbers, and tight neutronic-thermal feedbacks. The research combines deterministic and high-fidelity Monte Carlo approaches coupled with subchannel thermal-hydraulic models to characterize steady-state, depletion, and transient behaviour. The resulting benchmark activities will deliver a unique database for tool validation and cross-comparison among European institutions. Ultimately, these studies will support the development of reliable methodologies for the safety assessment and licensing of next-generation boron-free SMR cores in Europe.

Keywords: PRATIC, LDR-50, Monte Carlo, Deterministic, Depletion

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) have attracted growing attention within the nuclear community as a promising option to complement large-scale reactors and support the transition towards low-carbon energy systems [1]. Their modularity, enhanced reliance on passive safety features, and potential for co-generation applications such as district heating, desalination, and hydrogen production, make them particularly suited to diverse energy needs. Several national and international initiatives have therefore emerged to assess their technological, safety, and societal implications, reflecting the strategic role of SMRs in future nuclear deployment. As part of the European driven R&D efforts in this direction, the EASI-SMR (Ensuring Assessment of Safety Innovations for Small Modular Reactors) project was launched in 2024 to address key safety and licensing challenges specific to

*victor.sanchez@kit.edu

European light-water SMR designs [2], [3]. Funded under the Horizon Europe Euratom Programme (2024–2028), EASI-SMR addresses the safety challenges and innovative features of light-water SMR concepts foreseen for deployment in Europe. Coordinated by Électricité de France (EDF), the project brings together 38 partners from 16 European countries belonging to industry, research organizations, and regulators with the objective of developing a robust framework to address both technological and societal challenges with the overarching goal of ensuring that the next generation of SMRs can achieve the highest levels of safety and public acceptance in the European context.

The activities within the EASI-SMR project are organized into nine Work Packages (WPs) that collectively address the main challenges associated with the development and deployment of European small modular reactors. In particular, one WP is focused to advanced core physics studies of boron-free SMR designs, with the aim of improving understanding of their neutronic behavior and validating industrial analysis tools against high-fidelity ones. The purpose of this paper is to present the main objectives, the work program and the current status of the ongoing investigations, highlighting the preliminary results achieved and the expected outcomes of the core physics studies.

2. ADVANCED CORE PHYSICS STUDIES WITHIN EASI-SMR

Numerous industrial SMR designs are currently under development across the globe. Among these, some projects focus on the development of soluble-boron-free (SBF) PWR cores (i.e., Rolls Royce SMR, CAREM, etc.) [1]. SBF reactor cores are typically chosen to avoid the complications associated with using soluble boron, such as corrosion of structural materials, large volumes of liquid radioactive waste, potential boron dilution accidents, degradation of the moderator temperature coefficient, and the need for boron control and water purification systems. As a result, removing soluble boron from the primary coolant system provides several benefits by simplifying reactor operation and maintenance. Currently, one method to compensate for excess reactivity in SBF reactor cores is the use of burnable absorbers (such as gadolinium-poisoned fuel rods) and control rods. However, despite the advantages of SBF operation, its reliance on control rods leads to significant variations in power distribution during the irradiation cycle. Moreover, the use of poisoned fuel rods often results in an uneven distribution of burnable poisons within the core, making it more challenging to achieve a uniform radial power distribution within a fuel assembly of both larger PWR- and SMR-cores. These challenges are further amplified in SMRs due to their smaller size and the common use of heavy reflectors (mainly made of steel) to extend the cycle length and flatten the power distribution. Hence, the behaviour of SMR cores may differ significantly from that of larger PWRs, necessitating a detailed examination of the assumptions used in the neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculation schemes. In this context, one of the EASI-SMR Work Packages is specifically devoted to advanced core physics studies of SBF SMR-cores. Within this Work Package, a consortium of 12 partner organisations, led by KIT and including research institutions (KIT, CEA, VTT, HZDR, UJV, PSI), industry partners (TRACTEBEL, FRAMATOME, EDF), and regulatory bodies (ASNR, GRS, SSTC), is conducting two main benchmark exercises. The benchmarks focus on the PRATIC core developed by CEA [4] and on the LDR lite [5], a public benchmark version of the LDR-50 reactor developed originally at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd and now being commercialized by Steady Energy Oy.

2.1. The PRATIC core

The PRATIC (*Petit REP Académique pour Tester, Innover et Concevoir*) core is a SBF pressurized water reactor concept developed as an academic benchmark for code validation. It represents a 350 MWth SMR core, consisting of 57 fuel assemblies in a typical 17×17 PWR configuration, arranged into three enrichment zones (2.5, 3.5, and 5.0 wt% U-235), with varying fractions of gadolinium-bearing rods employed for reactivity control throughout the irradiation cycle. The design integrates grey and black control rod banks, axial and radial reflectors, and is optimized for a cycle length of ~1.9 years with an average discharge burnup of about 34 GWd/t. Thanks to its compact size and absence of soluble boron, PRATIC provides a challenging and realistic framework to investigate reactivity management, spectral effects, and transient behaviour, and has become a reference case for benchmarking advanced core physics methods in the context of SMR development. In general, the technological solutions employed in PRATIC, such as fuel type, burnable absorbers, control rods, and reflectors, are consistent with those found in established PWR industrial concepts.

During the first phase of the EASI-SMR project, extensive work has been performed to further modify the details of the specifications of the PRATIC core with respect to [4] and a detailed description of this activity can be found in [6]. For the purpose of the EASI-SMR core physics studies, the PRATIC benchmark specifications consist of two components (shown in Fig. 1), as follows:

- A "start-up" core made entirely of fresh fuel assemblies;
- An "equilibrium" core, which is composed of half fresh fuel assemblies and half fuel assemblies that have undergone one cycle of irradiation.

The term "equilibrium cycle" is not really appropriate for this benchmark. It is in fact an assembly loading pattern within the core that is identical for all cycles from number 2 onwards. What distinguishes the start-up core from the equilibrium core is the assembly loading patterns within the core.

E2= UOX 2.8%; 4 Gd pins w/2% Gd₂O₃ + 4 Gd pins w/8% Gd₂O₃
 E1= UOX 5.0%; 28 Gd pins w/8% Gd₂O₃
 I2= UOX 1.6%; 0 Gd pin
 I1= UOX 3.5%; 36 Gd pins w/8% Gd₂O₃
 C1= UOX 2.5%; 8 Gd pins w/8% Gd₂O₃

E1 and E2 = UOX 5.0% 28Gd pins w/8% Gd₂O₃
 I1 and I2 = UOX 3.5% 36Gd pins w/8% Gd₂O₃
 C1 = UOX 2.5% 8Gd pins w/8% Gd₂O₃

Figure 1. Loading pattern of the PRATIC start-up (left) and equilibrium (right) cores.

2.2. The LDR lite core

The LDR lite benchmark under investigations within the EASI-SMR project is as a public representation of the LDR-50 small modular reactor concept, initially developed at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd and currently being commercialized by Steady Energy Oy. LDR-50 is a 50 MWth low temperature and low-pressure light water reactor concept designed for heat production in applications such as district heating, low-pressure industrial steam, and potentially desalination. The design emphasizes simplicity, passive safety, and low operating parameters to facilitate licensing and deployment. The reactor has in-vessel control rod drives and the primary circuit is self-pressurizing. Primary coolant circulation is achieved through natural convection, eliminating the need for mechanical pumps. The design is boron free and long-term reactivity control is achieved by using grey control rods and burnable absorbers. The reactor core is housed within a concentric double-vessel configuration, where the inner vessel contains the fuel assemblies, and the outer vessel serves as a containment barrier. The annular space between the vessels is partially filled with water, which functions as a medium for passive decay heat removal in the event of a loss of active cooling. During normal operation, heat is transferred from the primary circuit to helical-coil steam generators.

Figure 2. Radial cross-section of the LDR lite reactor core model (left) and start-up core loading pattern (right).

2.3. Benchmark modelling strategies and computational tools

Within the EASI-SMR project, the two numerical cores presented above will be fully characterized both in steady-state and in transient conditions using different tools that combine solutions at different fidelity levels (Fig. 3). Industry-like (two step) methods based on diffusion implemented in different core solvers (SIMULATE5, APOLLO3®, PANTHER, PARCS, DYN3D, Ants, FENNECS) and advanced low order solutions (SP3) will be compared against high-fidelity reference solutions based on Monte Carlo neutronics (Serpent, TRIPOLI4 [7]) and subchannel thermal-hydraulics (SCF). As far as the work program, after the finalization of the benchmark specifications, the first phase of the activities will involve the characterization at beginning of cycle conditions (BOC). This is going to be performed in a two-step approach, namely *i*) a Hot Zero Power (HZP) exercise with the purpose to calibrate the neutronics models with imposed isothermal conditions and *ii*) several Hot Full Power (HFP) exercises (different core configurations at different power levels) for the coupled multi-physics analyses for PRATIC while for LDR lite only a single HFP state is considered. After the full characterization at BOC, in the second phase of the studies the investigations of the two cores up to End of Cycle (EOC) conditions are planned. As for the BOC phase, also in this case a two-step approach is planned, based on *i*) a depletion benchmark considering all-rods-in in case (ARI) and all-rods-out (ARO) configurations starting with a fresh core with imposed TH conditions and *ii*) a multi-cycle depletion exercise, carried out at critical insertion of the control rods at every time step, to find the equilibrium (EqC) core and EOC conditions. The simulations up to the end of cycle (EOC) will also enable the evaluation of the spent fuel characteristics in terms of isotopic inventory, thereby providing the scientific community with additional insight into the specific features of the waste stream generated by light-water SMRs [10]. In parallel to the steady-state and depletion investigations, a dedicated task is also expected to define transient scenarios to be analyzed at both BOC and EqC. Typical accidents under discussion to be simulated include rod ejection/withdrawal and/or coolant front injection types, depending on the feasibility of such events in the two SMR core designs. For such simulations three different computational routes will be used, namely *i*) nodal diffusion solvers coupled with TH (SIMULATE5-K, PANTHER/CTF, PANTHER/TRACE, CRONOS2/THERMOC, APOLLO3®/THEDI, PARCS/CATHARE, Ants/SCF, DYN3D, FENNECS/ATHLET), *ii*) low order transport solvers coupled with subchannel codes (APOLLO3®/FLICA, DYN3D/SCF) and *iii*) advanced transport solvers coupled with subchannel codes (Serpent/SCF). Furthermore, all simulations for the two cores are going to be performed using either JEFF3.1.1 and ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data libraries (NDLs), according to their availability across the participating institutions.

Figure 3. Calculations schemes and tools used for the PRATIC and LDR50-lite simulations

3. PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS OF THE BENCHMARK ANALYSES

As far as the PRATIC core, after the finalization of the benchmark specifications [6], the neutron-physical characterization of the start-up core in steady-state conditions at beginning of life (BOL) with the different simulations tools is currently ongoing. According to the description of work presented in the previous paragraph, a hot zero power (HZIP) exercise is under investigation from the different partners with the purpose to calibrate the respective models taking into account only the neutronics effect with imposed isothermal conditions. During this first phase of the project, sensitivity analyses have been also conducted in order to assess the impact of using different modeling options in the different simulation tools on the accuracy of the results, while maintaining acceptable computational costs. These includes for example the energy collapsing schemes at the lattice level and also the multigroup representation of the nodal solutions in the different core solvers. At the lattice level, a good agreement between deterministic tools and the Serpent solutions have been generally found (Table I).

 Table I. k_{∞} of the different PRATIC start-up core fuel assemblies, ENDF/B-VII.1 results.

FA-type	CR insertion	CASMO5	APOLLO3 [®]	HELIOS	Serpent
C (UOX 2.5%; 8 Gd pins w/ 8% Gd2O3)	No	1.16954	1.17007	1.17218	1.17053 ± 0.00002
	Black	0.80894	0.80858	0.80430	0.80834 ± 0.00002
I1 (UOX 3.5%; 36 Gd pins w/ 8% Gd2O3)	No	0.93306	0.93278	0.93769	0.93362 ± 0.00002
	Grey	0.77296	0.77167	0.77208	0.77251 ± 0.00003
I2 (UOX 1.6%; no Gd)	No	1.18066	1.18173	1.18359	1.18238 ± 0.00001
	Black	0.72688	0.72765	0.72419	0.72672 ± 0.00003
E1 (UOX 5.0%; 28 Gd pins w/ 8% Gd2O3)	No	1.12589	1.12565	1.12922	1.12696 ± 0.00002
	Black	0.87078	0.86938	0.86543	0.87038 ± 0.00003
E2 (UOX 2.8%; 4 Gd pins w/ 2% Gd2O3 + 4 Gd pins w/ 8% Gd2O3)	No	1.21983	1.22067	1.22248	1.22112 ± 0.00003
	Grey	0.93624	0.93476	0.93296	0.93616 ± 0.00003
	Black	0.85276	0.85185	0.84739	0.85226 ± 0.00002

More details are given in the companion papers of this conference [9] and [10]. At the core level, as expected, it has been found that 4-group diffusion solutions (SIMULATE5) offer better accuracy, owing to their ability to account for the key characteristics of the small cores under consideration, such as high leakage, strong sensitivity to spectral effects, and tight coupling. This can be also highlighted by looking at the deviations between the CR worth prediction by different diffusion core solvers and the corresponding Serpent 2 solutions (Fig. 4). One can observe that 4-gr. solutions are generally better in agreement with the references, and this is particularly true in the ARI case, where 2-gr. Solutions (PANTHER, APOLLO3) show quite larger discrepancies. This can easily be explained by the fact that

in this configuration the absorber strongly dominates the flux distribution, making spectral fidelity particularly important. The 4-group diffusion model provides also a more accurate representation of the axial power profile at the top and bottom nodes (Fig. 4), as the additional energy groups allow the solver to capture spectral hardening due to neutron leakage at the core periphery. More details of core level analysis can be found in the companion papers of this conference [9] and [10].

Figure 4. Control rod worth (left) and relative deviation in the axial power profile with respect to the reference solutions (right), ENDF/B-VII.1 results.

A very good agreement between the deterministic and Monte Carlo solutions has also been observed for some cases in the prediction of the radial power maps (Fig. 5), with deviations in this case being less than 1%.

Figure 5. Normalized radial power distribution: deviation (%) between SIMULATE5 and Serpent in the case of control rods group 4 (G4) inserted (left) and control rods group 3 (G3) inserted (right) according to the control rod pattern shown.

The initial core of the LDR lite at BOL conditions is currently being analyzed by VTT, HZDR, and GRS. In this fresh core benchmark, two neutronics only states with fixed TH conditions and the HFP state with neutronics-TH coupling are modelled. The former two are the all-rods-out (ARO) state and a critical state with pre-defined control rod group insertions. Reference solutions are calculated with Serpent for the neutronics only states and with Serpent/SCF for the HFP state. The benchmark is solved with the following reduced order code systems: Ants/SCF (VTT), DYN3D (HZDR) and FENNECS/ATHLET (GRS). For all states, the effective multiplication factors along with axial, assembly, and pin power distributions are compared against Serpent reference results. In addition, control rod group worths are calculated from the ARO state, and moderator and fuel temperature reactivity coefficients from the critical state.

In order to demonstrate the results obtained so far, effective multiplication factors for the ARO and critical states calculated with Ants, DYN3D, and Serpent are presented in Table 2. Effective multiplication factors calculated with DYN3D are closer to the Serpent reference values compared to Ants. Root mean square (RMS) and maximum (MAX) differences between the relative power distributions estimated with the nodal diffusion solvers and Serpent are shown in Table 3. The differences have been evaluated based on local relative powers as $(\text{Solver-Serpent}) \times 100$. The RMS/MAX differences in the power distributions are slightly smaller for Ants compared to DYN3D. Both Ants and DYN3D utilized group constants calculated with Serpent. Finally, differences in the relative pin powers evaluated with Serpent/SCF and Ants/SCF are shown in Fig. 6 for a 45-degree symmetry sector of the core. The magnitude of the differences is similar to the neutronics only states. More thorough analysis of the results of the fresh core benchmark is presented in Ref. [9].

Table 2. Effective multiplication factors calculated with Ants, DYN3D and Serpent.

State	Ants (2 groups)	DYN3D (2 groups)	Serpent
ARO	1.07122	1.07176	1.07347 ± 0.00001
Critical state	1.00192	1.00267	1.00275 ± 0.00001

Table 3. Differences between the relative power distributions estimated with Ants/DYN3D and Serpent. Differences are given as RMS/MAX.

State	Distribution	Ants (2 groups)	DYN3D (2 groups)
ARO	Assembly	0.4 / 0.7	0.7 / 1.3
	Pin	0.7 / 2.6	1.0 / 6.0
	Axial	0.7 / 1.7	0.7 / 1.8
Critical state	Assembly	0.8 / 1.6	1.1 / 1.9
	Pin	1.2 / 3.9	1.5 / 6.6
	Axial	1.7 / 4.1	1.7 / 4.1

Figure 6. Differences between relative pin power distributions estimated with Serpent/SCF and Ants/SCF in the HFP state.

4. CONCLUSIONS

As part of European-driven R&D efforts supporting the safety assessment of SMR cores, the EASI-SMR project sees KIT leading a consortium of research institutions, industry partners, and safety authorities to perform advanced core physics studies on SBF SMRs. This research, carried out over a four-year period (2024–2028), aims to enhance understanding of neutronic behaviour, reactivity control, and coupled neutronic–thermal–hydraulic phenomena in compact, boron-free reactor cores. Two reference designs serve as the main numerical framework, namely the PRATIC core developed by CEA, representing an academic boron-free PWR configuration and the LDR lite, a public benchmark version of the LDR-50 district heating reactor. Both static, depletion and transient analyses of both core designs

are being performed using different computational tools including industry-like methods based on diffusion, and academic high-fidelity approaches based on transport (SP3, SN) and Monte Carlo methods applied stand-alone or coupled with thermal hydraulic codes (1D system and quasi-3D subchannel TH). The outcomes are expected to provide a comprehensive benchmark database and a methodological framework for the accurate modelling of boron-free SMR cores. The outcomes of such investigations are expected to provide a comprehensive benchmark database and a methodological framework for the accurate modelling of boron-free SMR cores, supporting the validation of advanced core analysis tools and contributing to the safety assessment and licensing readiness of next-generation European SMR designs.

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